

Comparative Analysis of Regulatory Frameworks: Software as a Medical Device Requirement in the USA and Europe

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Abstract:

Software has become a bigger role in medical devices and the general use of digital technology. It continues to increase in relevance as a stand-alone medical device. Ensuring the safety and efficacy of medical software is largely dependent on regulatory criteria for software as a medical device (SaMD). The usage of software in medical devices has grown in popularity as technology develops. Regulatory requirements for SaMD in the USA and Europe are given in this article. To prove the efficacy and safety of SaMD, a comprehensive clinical evaluation is required. Strong cybersecurity procedures are stressed, addressing vulnerabilities and protecting patient data, given the digital nature of SaMD. Healthcare is entering a revolutionary era because of the widespread use of Software as a Medical Devices (SaMD), which provides innovative approaches to patient monitoring, diagnosis, and treatment. This abstract provides a comprehensive overview of the regulatory landscape governing SaMD in the United States and Europe. This review compares regulations on software as medical devices in the United States of America (USA) and the European Union (EU).

Keywords: *Software as a Medical Device, Medical Device Software, regulatory requirements, regulation, clinical evaluation*

Introduction:

Software is now a crucial component of every product as technology continues to develop all elements of health care. It is widely integrated into digital platforms for both medical and non-medical uses. One of three forms of software connected to medical devices is software that, on its own, qualifies as a medical device. Software that is a part of a medical device (software in a medical device) and software used in the creation or upkeep of a medical device are the other two categories of software connected to medical devices¹. The number of people using digital tools, such as software programs, has greatly expanded in recent years. The Internet of Things (IoT) and the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) are two unstoppable trends that are sweeping the world². The use of software and applications in healthcare and wellness is constantly growing. This is clear from the rising popularity of Internet of Things (IoT) gadgets, professional and consumer smartphone apps, and even more advanced software used by healthcare professionals³. Software is playing a bigger role in medical equipment and the wider adoption of digital technology. Additionally, it is becoming more significant as a standalone medical device⁴.

What is SaMD?

The term "Software as a Medical Device" (SaMD) is defined as software intended to be used for one or more medical purposes that perform these purposes without being part of a hardware medical device. SaMD is a type of medical equipment that also comprises in-vitro diagnostic (IVD) equipment. SaMD can be used with non-medical (general-purpose) computing platforms³. The software does not fulfill the definition of SaMD if its intended purpose is to drive a hardware medical device. "Without being part of" signifies that software is not required for a hardware medical device to achieve its intended medical purpose⁵.

What is SaMD and what is it not?⁶

SaMD	NOT SaMD
Software that provides individual medical data can estimate the right medicine dose for a patient.	Software that operates a pacemaker
software that examines MRI pictures to identify and classify strokes.	Software that operates the motors in an infusion pump
Software that can monitor the growth of a mole over time and estimate its melanoma risk	Systematic use of electronic health records
Software that analyses data from various digital devices to identify epileptic seizure risk factors	Computer programs are used by the machines that construct medical equipment.
Being a website or mobile application	To assist a healthcare facility's administrative need

Rules and regulations for Software as a Medical Device in the USA:

For many years, the FDA in the United States has regulated the association between software and medical equipment. The FDA first examined whether or not some computer goods should be governed by the same regulations as medical devices in the late 1980s⁷. The FDA defines SaMD as a class of software intended for carrying out one or more medical tasks⁸.

SaMD categories:

SaMD category I:

Information for both serious and nonserious illnesses or ailments may be found in SaMD Category 1 software. Software that deals with serious diseases can only be categorized in category 1 if it has minimal effect and merely provides information to support clinical care rather than drive it. Otherwise, category 1 SaMD software offers details on less significant illnesses or medical issues.

Example: An illustration would be software that tracks exercise-related statistics.

SaMD Category II:

Depending on the importance of the information it gives to the medical decision, SaMD software in category II may be used to deliver information pertinent to a nonserious, serious, or critical healthcare condition or disease.

Example: a SaMD that measures the amount of carbohydrates ingested by a diabetic patient and measures their blood sugar level to determine the needed insulin dosage.

SaMD Category III:

SaMD software that supports clinical management for a critical condition or offers information to treat or diagnose dangerous conditions is included in Category III.

Example: SaMD is used to create preventative intervention plans by analyzing individual data from groups that are at risk for developing a certain form of cancer.

SaMD category IV:

Software classified as SaMD Category IV, which offers the knowledge required to treat or diagnose a serious medical condition, is thought to have a very high effect.

Example: SaMD that assesses skin lesion photos to assess cancerousness⁸.

Alternative regulatory approach:

USFDA software precertification pilot program:

The FDA's Total Product Lifecycle (TPLC) methodology allows for ongoing organization-wide excellence demonstration as well as the assessment and tracking of software products from premarket development to post-market performance⁹. The USFDA is using the voluntary software precertification pilot program as input for the creation of a future regulatory framework that would offer more simplified and effective regulatory monitoring of SaMD solutions. It wants to create a more effective and streamlined approach to SaMD regulation that is based on current standards of safety and effectiveness. This is because it recognizes that traditional medical device and IVD regulatory models are ill-suited to the short development timelines and constant change associated with SaMD products. It collaborates with industry pilot participants to develop, assess, and refine the Pre-Cert Program, an adaptable regulatory framework, to accomplish this aim. The proposed Pre-Cert Program places a significant emphasis on the software developer as opposed to individual products, which are the primary focus of the traditional pre-market regulatory review process. The USFDA envisions four key components:¹⁰

Fig 1: USFDA four key components of TPLC

Regulatory requirement:¹¹

Guidelines for the "content of premarket submissions for device software functions, 2021" have been released by the Food and Drug Administration of the United States. This guideline describes the data companies must submit with their applications to prove that the software on their devices is secure and suitable for the purpose for which it was designed.

Software documentation elements	Basic documentation level	Enhance documentation level
Documentation-level evaluation	A statement indicating the appropriate documentation level and a description of the rationale for the level.	
Software description	Software description, including an overview of operationally significant software features, analyses, input, and outputs.	
System and software architecture design chart	Comprehensive diagrams showing the links between the modules, layers, and interfaces that make up the device, the data inputs and outputs, the data flow, and how users or other products interact with the software and system	
Risk management file	Risk management plan and risk management report	
Software requirement specification	The entire documentation, which includes enough details to comprehend the information's traceability to the other software documentation pieces and describes the requirements or expectations for a system or piece of software, presented in an orderly manner	
Software design specification	none	The complete documentation includes enough details to enable the FDA to comprehend the technical design of the software's operation, how the software design accurately and fully complies with all SRS requirements, and how the software's intended use, functionality, safety, and efficacy relate to the SRS.
Software development and maintenance practice	A declaration of conformity to IEC 62304 OR an overview of the maintenance and configuration management tasks as well as the life cycle development strategy.	Complete configuration management and maintenance plan documentation in addition to basic documentation level

Fig 2: Outline of recommended documentation for SaMD in USA:¹¹

Clinical evaluation:

The FDA released guidance on the clinical evaluation of SaMD with the same text and presentation as the IMDRF guidance. Three components of SaMD clinical evaluation:¹²

valid clinical association	analytical validation	clinical validation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • does your SaMD output have a valid clinical association with the targeted clinical condition of your SaMD? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can your SaMD process input data accurately, reliably and precisely to generate output data? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • can your intended purpose for the target population in the context of clinical care be achieved through the use of your SaMD's accurate, reliable, and precise output data?

Fig 3: SaMD clinical evaluation

SaMD clinical evaluation process:

Clinical evaluation is a systematic process for the ongoing generation, collection, analysis, and assessment of clinical data related to a SaMD to generate evidence of its clinical association and performance metrics when used as intended by the manufacturer. The purpose of the following processes is to assist SaMD manufacturers in producing evidence for their device clinical assessments. It contains information, definitions, and associations with significant methods and resources that can help manufacturers provide the appropriate kind of proof.

1. Valid clinical association: check the validity of the evidence supporting the relationship between the SaMD output and the ideal clinical state.
2. Analytical validation: generate evidence demonstrating that the output of the SaMD meets the technical specifications and expectations outlined by the manufacturer.

- Clinical validation: generate evidence that the SaMD has been evaluated in the intended population and for the intended use and that it enables users to achieve clinically significant outcomes through consistent and dependable usage¹³.

Rules and regulations for Software as a Medical Device in Europe:

Instead of referring to SaMD, the EU uses the word “medical device software (MDSW)”¹⁴. MDR rule 11 defines medical device software for classifying purposes. Both hardware and software-only devices that are essential components of MDSW are covered by this rule.¹⁵ SaMD and MDSW each serve one or more separate medical purposes, which means that the software serves a function other than controlling a medical device¹⁶. Medical Device Software (MDSW), according to the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) of the European Commission, is software designed to be used, either alone or in conjunction with, for a purpose listed in the definition of a "medical device" in Article 2(1) of Medical Device Regulation (EU) 2017/745. This definition applies whether or not the software is autonomous or influences or drives the use of a device.¹⁷The Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) of the European Commission has categorized medical device software into three classes;¹⁸

Intervention type	Treat or diagnose	Drive clinical management	Informs clinical management
Critical	III	IIb	IIb
Serious	IIb	IIa	IIa
Nonserious	IIa	IIa	IIa

Fig 4: MDS Classification

Regulatory requirement:

Software falling under the medical device definition according to this regulation and the guidance document that goes with it, MDCG 2019-11 qualification and classification of software, must adhere to the relevant general safety and performance requirements (GSPRs) as indicated in Annex I of the methodology disclose regulation.

MDSW legal manufacturers are required to provide a dossier, or technical document, for their product that includes the information specified in Annex II and III of the MDR to prove compliance with GSPRs. One of the following general fields is the focus of applicable GSPRs:

- Criteria for the Quality Management System (QMS)
- Requirements for Risk Management Systems (RMS)
- Requirements for clinical evaluation and post-market surveillance
- Usability requirements¹⁹

Quality management system requirements:

Developers of Medical Device Software (MDSW) must adhere to a Quality Management System (QMS) approach. The majority of medical device manufacturers want to have their QMS certified to ISO 13485, even though it is not required for CE marking. If the business has created and implemented a QMS and carried out a thorough audit, this certification can be obtained from a Notified Body that the MDR has authorized.

Risk management system requirements:

Ensuring that possible hazards are recognized, categorized, and minimized without negatively impacting the device's risk-benefit ratio is the primary objective of an RMS. To achieve this, the manufacturer must create and put into action a risk management strategy in which it accurately identifies all hazards related to the device, specifies the necessary risk mitigation measures, and evaluates the effectiveness of those measures. The ISO 14971 Medical Devices - Application of risk management to medical devices is often followed in the conduct of this investigation.

Clinical evaluation and post-market surveillance requirements:

The MDCG 2020-1, guidelines for the clinical assessment of MDSWs, and a clinical evaluation report that includes the following details must all be followed while conducting an MDSW's clinical evaluation:

- An accurate clinical correlation, often established through literature references, between the program and the intended clinical condition or physiological state.
- a data processing demonstration of the software's analytical validation, showing its capability.
- a clinical validation that assures accurate and dependable software output in a specific clinical context.

Usability requirements:

Although human factors engineering or usability criteria are not unique to MDSW, SW developers still need to make sure that the user interface minimizes the number of user mistakes that might occur. Usability tests must be organized and carried out in compliance with IEC 62366 to do this medical equipment - Part 1: Usability engineering applied to medical equipment.

Software lifecycle requirements:

IEC 62304 Medical device software - Software life cycle methods provide an overview of the software lifecycle process. It should be noted that this standard does not offer guidance on how the various stages of software development should be executed. However, it does lay out a set of steps that software developers must follow. This responsibility is on the software developer to draft a strategy for software development that specifies exactly when and how these procedures will be carried out.

Cybersecurity requirements:

The MDR's Annex I specifically mention cybersecurity requirements concerning MDSW. However, other laws also apply, including the Cybersecurity Act, the Network Information Systems (NIS) Directive, and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The confidentiality of patient data and defense against other cyber threats are the two primary foci of cybersecurity requirements (i.e. hackers undermining the operation of MD with malicious intent). Regarding the RMS, it is recommended to create an Information Security Management System (ISMS). Within this system, a cybersecurity management strategy should be designed and executed, identifying all associated risks and putting in place suitable steps to mitigate them. It is crucial to remember that safety risks may be increased by cybersecurity risk mitigation strategies, and this has to be included in the overall risk management strategy for MDSW development. Figure 1 shows an overview of the EU Regulatory Environment for MDSW Development.

Clinical evaluation:

Clinical evidence, according to the MDR, has to be based on a very strict definition of clinical data from an original or equivalent device, with clinical data coming mainly from clinical investigations. In addition, the quality of the available post-market surveillance clinical data is not considered good enough. This was problematic for a lot of medical devices with "sufficient clinical evidence" but where the clinical data did not meet the MDR requirements or the expectations of the reviewers. Three guidance documents were developed to circumvent the problems:

- Guidelines on adequate clinical evidence for legacy devices provided by MDCG 2020-6.²⁰
- MDCG 2020-5 guidelines for clinical evaluation.²¹
- MDCG 2020-1 guidelines for the clinical (MDR) or performance (IVDR) assessment of software used in medical devices.²²

General principles of the MDSW clinical evaluation (MDR): MDCG 2020-1:²³ Performance Evaluation (IVDR) and Clinical Evaluation (MDR) are continuous processes that are carried out during an MDSW's life cycle. It is an ongoing, visible, iterative, and systematic process that is a component of a device's quality management system. Every MDSW should consider these three important factors while assembling clinical evidence:

1. Valid clinical association / scientific validity:

The MDSW's output (e.g. concept, conclusion, calculations) based on the inputs and algorithms selected, is associated with the targeted physiological state or clinical condition. This association should be well-founded or clinically accepted. The Valid clinical association / scientific validity of an MDSW should demonstrate that it corresponds to the clinical situation, condition, indication, or parameter defined in the intended purpose of the MDSW.

2. technical performance / analytical performance:

The process of validating the technical and analytical performance involves showcasing the MDSW's capability to precisely, reliably, and accurately produce the desired output based on the input data. The technical

performance and analytical performance are validated by analysis and the presentation of impartial proof that the MDSW specifications meet the demands of users and their intended applications and that the implemented criteria can be reliably met.

3. clinical performance:

The capacity of an MDSW to provide clinically meaningful output in line with the intended goal is what is meant to be demonstrated as validation of the clinical performance. A beneficial influence on a person's health represented in terms of measurable, patient-relevant clinical outcome(s), such as outcome(s) linked to diagnosis, risk prediction, or treatment response prediction, is what defines an MDSW's clinical relevance.²⁷

Comparison of regulatory requirements of software as a medical device in the USA and Europe:

	USA	EUROPE
Regulatory authority	USFDA	EMA
Recognition of software medical device	In 1989, the FDA recognized software-based products as devices with the publication of the first "Policy for the Regulation of Computer Products" guidance document.	In 2009, the EU included the term "software" in the EU definition of a medical device
Definition	Software as a Medical Device" (SaMD) is defined as software intended to be used for one or more medical purposes that perform these purposes without being part of a hardware medical device	According to MDCG 2019-11, "Medical device software is software that is intended to be used, alone or in combination, for a purpose as specified in the definition of a "medical device" in the medical devices regulation (MDR)"
Synonyms for SaMD in various countries	Standalone software as a medical device	Medical device software
Guideline	FDA has collaborated with IMDRF to develop international guidelines for SaMD. Software as a Medical Device (SaMD): Key Definitions (2013) SaMD: Application of Quality Management System (2013) SaMD: Possible Framework for Risk Categorization and Corresponding Considerations (2014) Clinical Evaluation of SaMD (2017) SaMD: Clinical Evidence for Emerging Technologies (2017) Other: Software Pre-Cert Program, Guidance for Industry, Food and Drug Administration Staff, and Other Stakeholders (2021) Content of Premarket Submissions for Device Software Functions, 2021	MEDDEV 2.1/6 Guidelines on the qualification and classification of standalone software used in healthcare within the regulatory framework of medical devices (2012) MEDDEV 2.1/3 Guidelines on medical devices incorporating software (2017) MEDDEV 2.1/4 Guidelines on the classification of standalone software used in healthcare (2017) Guideline on the Qualification and Classification of Software in Regulation (EU) 2017/745 – MDCG 2019- 11 (2019) Guidance on the qualification and classification of software as a medical device (SaMD) (2020) Guidelines on Digital Health Technologies and Intended uses (2021) MDCG 2020-1 guidance on clinical (MDR) or performance evaluation of medical device software
Risk-based classification for software as a medical device	Category I, Category II, Category III, Category IV	Class I Class IIa Class IIb Class III
SaMD Classification based on	1. Significance of the information provided by the SaMD to the healthcare decision 2. State of the healthcare situation or condition that the SaMD is intended for Critical situation or condition OR Serious situation or condition	1. Significance of the information provided by the SaMD to the healthcare decision 2. State of the healthcare situation or condition that the SaMD is intended for Critical situation or condition OR Serious situation or condition
Alternative pathway for SaMD approval	Software Precertification Pilot Program: 1. Pre-Certification Through an Excellence Appraisal; 2. Review Pathway Determination; 3. Streamlined Review; and 4. Real World Performance	No alternative pathway, get approval by normal medical device process
Level of practice to control software like a medical equipment	best practice adapted	best practice adopted, but further improvements are recommended

Conclusion:

Both the FDA and EU employ risk-based classification systems to categorize SaMD. However, the criteria for classification may differ slightly between the two regions, leading to variations in regulatory requirements for different types of SaMD. Both regions require comprehensive documentation and quality management systems. In the USA, this is outlined in the Quality System Regulation (QSR), while in Europe, conformity assessment procedures, including the involvement of notified bodies, are crucial. In the USA, SaMD generally requires pre-market submission, with the type of submission (e.g., 510(k), De Novo, or PMA) determined by the device's classification and risk level. In Europe, SaMD must undergo conformity assessment procedures, involving conformity assessment bodies, before receiving a CE mark for market access. In conclusion, while both the USA and Europe aim to ensure the safety, efficacy, and quality of SaMD, there are differences in their regulatory frameworks. The FDA's approach may offer greater flexibility for innovation, while the EU's framework provides a more structured and standardized process. Understanding these similarities and differences is crucial for SaMD developers seeking to navigate global regulatory requirements effectively.

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